

Title: ETHIOPIAN SIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING PLATFORM USING DETECTION

A Senior project submitted to the department of Computer Science and Engineering

School of Electrical Engineering and Computing

Presented in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for Bachelor Degree

in Computer Science and Engineering

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Feb 3, 2023

Adama, Ethiopia

Table of Contents

ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Background of the project	2
1.2. Statement of the problem	3
1.3. Objective of the project	4
1.3.1. General Objective	4
1.3.2. Specific objective	4
1.4. Scope of the project	5
1.5. Limitation of the project	5
1.6. Feasibility study	6
1.6.1. Technical Feasibility	6
1.6.2. Financial Feasibility	6
1.6.3. Market Feasibility	6
1.6.4. Operational Feasibility.....	6
1.7. Significance of the project.....	7
1.8. Beneficiaries of the project	7
1.9. Proposed methodology	8
1.10. Development tools	10
1.11. Project Deliverables.....	11
1.12. Cost breakdown	12
1.13. Team Composition.....	12
1.14. Task and Schedule	13
2. EXISTING SYSTEMS	14
2.1. Major function of the existing system	14
2.2. Significance of the existing system	15
2.3. Drawback of the existing system	15
2.4. literature review.....	16
2.4.1. Sign Language	16
2.4.2. Ethiopian Sign Language.....	17
2.4.3. SL Transcription	19
2.5. Business Logic of the current system	19
3. PROPOSED SYSTEM	21
3.1. Overview.....	21
3.2. Functional requirement.....	21
3.3. Non-functional Requirement	21
3.4. System Scenario	23
3.5. Use case Model.....	30
3.5.1. Use case diagram	31

3.5.2. Use case description	32
3.6. Object Model.....	37
3.6.1. Class Diagram.....	37
3.7. Data Dictionary	40
3.8. Dynamic Model	42
3.8.1. Sequence Diagram.....	42
3.8.2. Activity Diagram	52
3.8.3. State chart Diagram	57
4. SYSTEM DESIGN	60
4.1. Overview of the System	60
4.2. Purpose of the System Design	60
4.3. Design Goals	60
4.3.1. Performance.....	60
4.3.2. Dependability	60
4.3.3. Maintenance.....	61
4.3.4. End user	61
4.4. Proposed System Architecture	61
4.5. Subsystem Decomposition	62
4.6. Subsystem Description	63
4.7. Persistent Data Management	64
4.8. Components Diagram.....	68
4.9. Database Design	69
1.10. Access Control.....	70
5. MACHINE LEARNING METHODOLOGY	71
5.1. Method of applications	71
5.2. Major components used	72
5.3. Steps in development of Sign Language detection	74
6. IMPLEMENTATION	79
6.1. Overview.....	79
6.2. Coding Standard.....	79
6.3. Prototype	80
6.4. Implementation Detail.....	80
6.4.1. Client-side	80
6.4.2. Server Side	81
6.5. Deployment.....	82
6.6. User Interface Design	84
REFERENCE	88

list of Tables

TABLE 1 - PROJECT DELIVERABLES.....	11
TABLE 2 - COST BREAKDOWN.....	12
TABLE 3 - TEAM COMPOSITION	12
TABLE 4 - TASK AND SCHEDULE	13

Table of Figures

FIGURE 1 - WORKFLOW OF THE PROJECT.....	9
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ABSTRACT

The proposed project aims at developing an Ethiopian Sign Language (ESL) Learning Platform. The purpose of this platform is to facilitate the teaching and learning of ESL for both students and teachers, as well as to give the hearing-impaired community in Ethiopia a sense of identity and self-confidence.

This platform will provide a comprehensive, interactive and user-friendly environment that includes lessons and activities to help users understand and master the language. Furthermore, the platform will include audio and text-based courses, as well as quizzes and games, to help users further enhance their skills and to make the learning process more engaging. ESL teachers can also use the platform to conduct classes and group activities.

The proposed platform will also enable direct communication between hearing-impaired and hearing users, by providing a chat function, which will allow for seamless communication and sharing of information between both communities. Additionally, the platform will serve as a repository for the Deaf community, where they can share stories, experiences and their culture, thus allowing them to express themselves and connect with other members of the community.

1. INTRODUCTION

As a social being, humans have developed a unique way to communicate and transfer accumulated knowledge from generation to generation. It's either done with written or spoken. Spoken communication (word of mouth) includes oral, speech and voice and hearing. In this process, a person has to listen and produce voice. This is where sign language plays a big role for people with hearing loss. It bridges the gap between speaking and listening.

A person is said to have hearing loss if they are not able to hear as well as someone with normal hearing, meaning hearing thresholds of 20 dB or better in both ears. Major causes of hearing loss include congenital or early onset childhood hearing loss, chronic middle ear infections, noise-induced hearing loss, age-related hearing loss, and ototoxic drugs that damage the inner ear. ^[1]

The impacts of hearing loss are broad and can be profound. They include a loss of the ability to communicate with others delayed language development in children, which can lead to social isolation, loneliness and frustration, particularly among older people with hearing loss. When people feel ashamed of their hearing loss, they may refuse to acknowledge it, which can lead to disruptions in their treatment. At the same time, being uneducated, they have hard time communicating with other hearing-impaired or hearing people.

Globally, over 20% of the world population is said to live with hearing loss and 430 million have disabling hearing loss. In Ethiopia alone, more than five million people live with this condition. ^[1] Many live unnoticed with this condition and are given too little to none care. Many areas lack sufficient accommodations for hearing loss, which effect academic performance and options for employment. Children with hearing loss and deafness in Ethiopia rarely receive any schooling. Sign language schooling is also limited to some places and the number of students who in these institutions are only in thousands. As a result, they stay at home and work only on labor demanding jobs.

Understanding that verbal communication is one of the ways in learning, living and growth, the proposed platform focuses on providing contents on learning sign language – Ethiopian sign language. The system is designed to resolve the communication barrier that drags people with hearing loss from ever showing their full potential. With interactive visuals and a robust library, anyone who wants to learn sign language can easily learn basic or medium communication skills. At the same time, the system could be used as a chatting platform where a hearing-impaired person can sign to hearing person or a hearing person can type or voice a message that could be converted to a sign. This way makes the lives of hearing-impaired people easy and reduces the impact of stigma of hearing loss. Let's face it; people with hearing loss are also humans; they have their own personal and social problems aside from being able to communicate spoken language. Automating the sign language process then makes the life of millions easy

1.1. Background of the project

This project is proposed to develop an Ethiopian Sign Language (EthSL) learning platform to help individuals to learn effective Ethiopian Sign Language. Current Amharic sign language studies have revealed that there is a dearth of materials and resources to facilitate the teaching of Ethiopian Sign Language. There are very few comprehensive, easy to use and widely available platforms that teach Ethiopian Sign Language. It happens that many researchers have done researches to help overcome this problem by coming up with different ideas that could help the hearing-impaired community interact with the rest of the society: Among the researches are Machine Translation System for Amharic Text to Ethiopian Sign Language^[7] and A Real-Time Ethiopian Sign Language to Audio Converter^[6]. However, in the abundance of research papers stating solutions for the community, we have come to find that there is void in implementing those researches.

The Ethiopian Sign Language platform will be designed to fill this void. It will be web-based application or mobile app which will enable users to learn the language by all users to learn sign language at their own pace, regardless of their geographical location. This will be especially useful to those with hearing impairments who are unable to access conventional classroom environment and hearing people that want to learn the language. From all of the Ethiopian sign language we picked specifically Amharic language for the data collection process. The platform will also be beneficial to individuals who want to incorporate sign language into their daily lives.

To ensure the success of this project, the team will conduct user testing and surveys with existing sign language communities to understand the user experience and preferences when utilizing the platform.

1.2. Statement of the problem

As discussed in the introduction, hearing loss creates many impacts on a person's life or their family. Life style and work conditions shift due to not being able to communicate with others. Family members struggle to learn and communicate with hearing-impaired person. Although it's expected that at least one family member with hearing has to learn sign language, the time and circumstances affect the learning process. If that member has a job schedule that contradicts with the learning process, it takes time for the hearing-impaired person to fully express themselves in the family. This impacts the family relationship greatly.

On the other hand, very few institutions give sign language courses. They are either kept in some governmental elementary schools or especial ED schools. Although the number of hearing-impaired people is high, because of not many hearing people are educated, they only have a small circle to socialize. This is because of small access to sign language education in their community. In Ethiopia, specially observed in Addis Ababa and Adama, the institutions are very few. As a result, access to proper sign language education has become a concern.

The major problem that this paper wants to address is that there aren't many digital data available in the sign language study. There has been works in the English sign language but Ethiopian sign language still has areas of research and development. Few Amharic sign languages are available and their models focus on words than grammar.

In this proposal, a web-based application is presented here to help anyone who wants to learn sign language. In addition, it creates a data for future research and development in the area of sign language, especially Ethiopian sign language.

1.3. Objective of the project

1.3.1. General Objective

The objective of this project is to develop Ethiopian Sign Language Learning Platform.

1.3.2. Specific objective

Specific objective of the project is:

- Gathering relevant resources form different data resources
- Do research on the hearing-impaired on how they learned the Ethiopian sign language
- Create learning dataset from gathered resources
- Research how the grammar works on Ethiopian sign language
- Prepare questionnaires for our research on schools that teach the Ethiopian sign language
- Integrate the detection on quizzes so the app is interactive with the user
- Organize courses into Beginner, Intermediate and advanced
- Create a dictionary for the Ethiopian sign language that user can search any word they want either in text

1.4. Scope of the project

The scope of this project will be to develop a web app that helps users that are hearing or non-deaf people to learn Ethiopian sign language by accurately detecting and recognizing hand gestures made by individuals. There are two features in this app. One is a learning platform with modules and categorized courses that have tutorials, exercises based on machine learning that uses images and video detection to give the correct answer. The other feature is a Classrooms feature that helps users engage in a more in depth learning with actual live teachers.

To make the learning more reactive and fun we will use machine language mostly deep learning to detect sign language and figure out if the signs are correct or not by recognizing a wide variety of hand gestures associated with Ethiopian sign language. It should also be able to convert the hand gestures into text that can be read by a computer.

1.5. Limitation of the project

Scope of the project

At the heart of our project lies a powerful vision—to create a transformative video chat app specifically designed for the unique needs of the hearing-impaired community. We aspire to empower individuals by providing them with a seamless platform that fosters communication, connection, and limitless possibilities. Though we encounter the challenge of limited research and resources in Ethiopian sign language, we see this as an opportunity to forge a different path, to pioneer a learning platform that paves the way towards our ultimate goal. By building this remarkable platform infused with cutting-edge detection capabilities, we lay the groundwork for a future where everyone can effortlessly learn and express themselves, bringing us one step closer to realizing our extraordinary vision. Together, let's embark on this remarkable journey, breaking barriers and creating a world where communication knows no bounds.

Classroom, Notification, Statistical Reports and Dictionary Functionalities

Due to exit-exam this functionality is not implemented fully (i.e. 70%). back-end need some additional time to complete since we have been taking exit exam meetings and preparation exams it is difficult to implement it 100%. But all the classroom's front-end is fully implemented

Machine Learning Implementation Techniques

Due to lack of resources and performance issues we were forced to user other ML methodologies which is updated in this document.

Machine Learning Integration

We have encountered a significant challenge in our endeavor to integrate machine learning (ML) with the front-end of our system. Despite our best efforts, we regret to inform you that we may face limitations in implementing this integration due to issues related to ML hosting and a lack of available front-end integration methods. We understand the importance of seamless integration between ML and the front-end for optimal system performance, and we deeply regret any inconvenience this limitation may cause. Our team continues to explore alternative solutions and avenues to overcome this obstacle and provide the best possible user experience.

1.6. Feasibility study

1.6.1. Technical Feasibility

The team has all the skills to develop this system without any difficulty since the team has studied the required methodologies and tools. The team use tools which are useful for technical feasibility like Front-end frameworks, Node.js, REST API and CRUD operations for user management, learning management system (LMS) and content management system (CMS). Even though the team have all the need skills we are having difficulties on getting GPU for our Machine learning system.

1.6.2. Financial Feasibility

The platform or application developed here is partially fiscally viable. The software tools used to develop are available at a low cost or for free as an open-source. The financial difficulty starts when it comes to hardware tools used in this project; tools like a server, computers with GPU and sign language materials. These tools are expensive or unavailable for the team to acquire personally. The team hopes that these issues could be solved with the help of the university and other affiliated parties.

1.6.3. Market Feasibility

The digital learning platform has become the new way for schools, institutions and professionals to give contents and courses remotely without the need to gather in one place. The proposed system here just adds to this new market that's untouched specially in the context of Ethiopia. In addition, personalized learning has also become popular as smartphones and laptops are easily accessible. This makes this platform usable by many users. If hardware limitations are fixed, since the statistics shows 5% of Ethiopian population are partially or totally hearing-impaired so the team expects a minimum of 10,000 users for the first launch and active users in the thousand.

1.6.4. Operational Feasibility

This proposed system could operate and be used as a personal application, as an e-learning system in schools or organizations and as a research tool for future development in the sign language industry. As it's a language platform, translation from a sign language to a word or text could be limited to some languages like Amharic and English. However, the team expects for the system to be translated to other additional languages. The system won't have problems in policies and legislation of the privacy of users or the contents used in the development. Since the system is new to the Ethiopian market and helps minorities, the proposed system is expected to be accepted by affiliated institutions.

1.7. Significance of the project

The web or mobile app we are developing is a way for hearing-impaired or hearing people like us to learn Ethiopian Sign Language and try to understand the hearing-impaired community and communicate with them too.

Generally, our main goals or our final achievements are:

- To prepare well documented research documentations
- Solving problems using Machine Learning and latest technologies
- Making online learning platform
- Facilitating for video chat platform
- Building hearing-impaired community

1.8. Beneficiaries of the project

We believe this project can enhance the lives of many hearing-impaired communities by allowing them learn remotely, families can easily learn sign language to communicate with their child, and live their life without having to rely on others to translate for them so that others can understand them with the aid of this technology.

Here are some organizations and members who will take the advantage: -

- Hearing-impaired communities
- Family members with a hearing-impaired member
- Ethiopian National Association of the Deaf (ENAD)
- Interested groups or people
- Government and private schools
- Organizations

1.9. Proposed methodology

Nowadays the internet is not that much costly as the previous years so making this platform an online system would not be an obstacle.

In general, we are going to use Agile Methodology and we have 4 phases which are:

- A deep understanding of Ethiopian Sign Language,
- ML (machine learning) process,
- Authentication and authorization or REST API, and
- Front-end development.

Our first approach for the first version would be focusing on the Web platform. In order to make this platform we need to have a deep understanding of the current sign language learning methods, and what limitations they have (hearing impaired community) in communicating or learning or in general intensive research is needed to start this project. The research will use observational, experimental, and questionnaire methodology.

After our intensive research is completed, the next phase would be organizing the gathered research and proceeding to the next phase which would be the machine learning process. In this phase we have gotten the input needed to start the machine learning processes so the ML process can be done.

When the ML process is completed, we proceed to the next phase which is REST API. This phase handles every request and makes sure every request sent is authenticated or not based on the subscription plans and obviously, it will handle the sign-up / sign-in process.

The REST API will also have CRUD operations for user management, learning management system (LMS) and content management system (CMS).

And finally, for the Front-end we have dynamic choices like making mobile apps using Flutter and making web platforms by using frameworks like Angular or ReactJS. We have found some issues while testing for beta purposes. Problems like the Graphics card is required in order to use our system and it needs some time for initial compilation (30 sec of compilation time). So based on this problem we will try to optimize the compilation time and graphics card issues by trying all possible options we got.

To finalize, our system will have the latest encryption algorithms for authentication and authorization and make it as light as possible which means any user should easily understand and users interactive.

Figure 1 - Workflow of the project

1.10. Development tools

The development tools to be used in the execution of this project are as follows.

- ✓ **Node JS /Django:** back-end development refers to the development of server-side logic that powers websites and apps from behind the scenes. It includes all the code needed to build out the database, server, and application. From database migrations to API integrations to setting up the server-side technologies that make a website tick, a back-end web developer may be the talent you need to get your next web project off the ground.
- ✓ **React:** A front-end developer architects and develops websites and applications using web technologies (i.e., HTML, CSS, DOM, and JavaScript or TS), which run on the Open Web Platform
- ✓ **Trello:** is the ultimate project management tool. Start up a board in seconds, automate tedious tasks, and collaborate anywhere, even on mobile.
- ✓ **TensorFlow:** An end-to-end machine learning platform; Prepare data. Use *TensorFlow* tools to process and load data; Build ML models
- ✓ **Jupyter notebook:** is the original web application for creating and sharing computational documents. It offers a simple, streamlined, document-centric experience.
- ✓ **MPHands** :The Media Pipe Hands pipeline integrates separate models hand components, each of which are optimized for their particular domain.
- ✓ **Pandas:** is a fast, powerful, flexible and easy to use open-source data analysis and manipulation tool, built on top of the Python programming language
- ✓ **Google Colab:** *Colab* notebooks allow you to combine executable code and rich text in a single document, along with images, HTML, LaTeX and more.
- ✓ **OpenCV:** provides a real-time optimized Computer Vision library, tools, and hardware. It also supports model execution for Machine Learning (ML)

1.11. Project Deliverables

Roll No.	Feature	Deliverable
1	Learning Portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Anyone can access it by creating an account or signing in using their credentials.• Any user can access the system-prepared lessons and exercises.
2	Exam Portal	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any user can take exam.• Get reports
3	Sign Language Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Any user can use sign language detection and interact with it using our AI Detection

Table 1 - Project Deliverables

1.12. Cost breakdown

Materials	Quantity	Unit price	Total price (birr)
Stationery materials			
Pen	10	20	200
Paper	2 pack	115	230
Notepad	2	50	100
Research			
Transportation	----	----	2,000
Questioner	----	----	150
Translator	1	5,000	5,000
Equipment			
Laptop	-----	----	-----
Flash drive	-----	----	-----
Utilities			
Internet	---	----	----
TOTAL			7,680

Table 2 - Cost Breakdown

1.13. Team Composition

Roll No.	Team member	ID Number	Responsibility
1	Eyob Birhanemeskel	UGR/17079/11	Back-end development, documentation, analysis, implementation and Testing
2	Feven Asnake	UGR/17106/11	Ui/UX design and machine learning model development (AI)
3	Nanati Oumer	UGR/17463/11	Front-end and Back-end development
4	Yeabsira Adem	UGR/17790/11	Front-end, Back-end and Security development, System design

Table 3 - Team Composition

1.14. Task and Schedule

Activity \ Time	December 22/2022	January 30/2022	February 28/2022	March 30/2022	April 30/2022	May 30/2022	July 20/2022
Research on the topic related to our topic	█						
Learn and brush up on JavaScript (Reactjs, Nodejs)	█						
Learn about basics of Data Science and Machine Learning	█						
Get familiar with the tools of ML like Google Collab, pandas, TensorFlow, karas, OpenCV		█					
Interview with the deaf community		█					
Work on the User Interface of the web app	█	█					
Start working on the documentation of the projects			█				
Finish the documentation			█				
Build and test a prototype UI/UX interface	█	█					
Finish on the front end (web app)			█				
Create data for the dataset				█			
Train the system using the dataset				█			
Test the detection is working				█	█		
Build and test a prototype that tastes the detection			█	█	█		
Work on the RestAPI					█		
Build and test the RestAPI					█		
Modify the app if possible						█	
Test the app on the deaf community		█	█	█	█	█	
Test the app on the non-deaf society		█	█	█	█	█	█

2. EXISTING SYSTEMS

2.1. Major function of the existing system

The current Ethiopian sign language mainly consists of three parts to create a clear understanding of the topic they want to convey. The first one is the use of manual features, which is by the movement of the hand shape and position, the second is the use of non-manual features, which is by the movement of facials (facial expression), and the third is the use of finger-spelling by spelled words or alphabets in their local gesture language.

Ethiopian Finger Spelling (Ethiopia manual alphabets): It is constantly used for representing proper nouns (personal, place, and objects), names with a context/stress based, signs with a country name, technical words, loan signs, and words from a foreign language “since there may not be predefined signs for them” and to represent different terminologies like subjective words. It has a total of 34 signs to represent all characters with their corresponding seven movements (derivatives). All the first Ge'ez characters are represented as a static image without any movement, and the rest (six characters) have their own different position of movement. Those six derivatives are representatives of vowels, whereas the hand configuration is for consonants.

The signer gives a sign by the combination of hand shape, hand orientation, and hand movements.

Hand Shape: The proper and exact image for the intended message can be described based on the right-hand shape of the signer. Each sign for characters (alphabets), numbers, words, and sentences have a different hand shape representation.

Hand Orientation: It refers to the palm position that the signer uses to represent something. Different orientations also represent different meanings; if the orientation changes, the meaning also changes. It can include the palm facing in, out, horizontally, left, up, or down.

Hand Location: the location of the hand can move in different directions to represent messages. Mostly, they used locations like around the forehead, chest, left to right, right to left, and some sinusoidal movements of the hand.

Hand Movement: Some signs have static images, and some have signed with motion. Knowing the proper movement of the hand, palm, and shoulder is very important for getting what we want to convey.

Non-manual Features: In addition to the hand position, movement, and location, the use of facial expression is included to clear the feelings and degree behind the word. This is like expressing the degree of happiness, surprise, and sadness.

2.2. Significance of the existing system

- In a traditional face-to-face learning scenario, classes are planned and structured according to a fixed schedule. This system of learning is thus more disciplined. Classroom learning also happens in a group setting and may spur more discussion, interaction, and involvement.
- Able to physically connect with students and teachers. Students can learn a lot from being in the company of their peers. This helps the student not have a sense of isolation.
- There is a range of classes for all age groups from preschool to university degree levels.

2.3. Drawback of the existing system

- One of the drawbacks of the current classroom education is that it allows students to attend classes that are restricted by geographical boundaries. They cannot learn from any location of their choice.
- The instructor leads the learning pace in a traditional classroom setting, and students are likely to learn passively.
- The grading system of the school is not consistent from place to place. For example, in **Adama No. 2 Deaf school** they teach sign language up to grade 4. And in **Degem Deaf School** they teach up to grade 2 even if they're in the same region Oromia.
- And if anyone wants to have a degree in Ethiopian sign language, they have to pass the university entrance exam with a 2.5 or above CGPA.
- Lack of online payment systems like
- And the scarcity of resources like textbooks, and online learning resources

From a digital perspective, the current system has some additional drawbacks:

- **Does Not use SaaS (Software as a Service):** SaaS is a software licensing and delivery model in which software is licensed on a subscription basis and is centrally hosted. SaaS is also known as "on-demand software" and Web-based/Web-hosted software.
- **Does Not use PaaS (Platform as a Service):** Platform as a service (**PaaS**) is a cloud computing model where a third-party provider delivers hardware and software tools to users over the internet. Usually, these tools are needed for application development. A PaaS provider hosts the hardware and software on its own infrastructure.
- Digital learning support system: there is almost no software or digitalized learning methods that support the Ethiopian Sign Language learning system.
- Don't have an organized and digitized data system

2.4. literature review

We have done a literature review in order to better understand existing work done directly or indirectly related to our work, analyzing the suitability of existing solutions to the problem, analyzing their possible extensions, or using some of their ideas to reach the solution. As part of this study, we explored state of art Machine Translation, explored existing frameworks and technologies, and analyzed them to find out the most suitable for devising the solution and then developing a prototype. We have searched for information from books, digital libraries, and search engines; such as ACM, IEEE, Springer, Inspec, and Google Scholar.

2.4.1. Sign Language

Sign Languages (SLs) are the first languages for the members of Deaf communities worldwide. Naturally occurring and indigenous languages can be as eloquent and as powerful as any spoken language through their visual–spatial modality. It is this alternative communicative channel that poses interesting challenges for the area of Machine Translation that lies outside of the general spoken language Machine Translation field.

2.4.1.1. Overview of Sign Language

SL research is still a relatively new area when compared to research on spoken languages. Significant study into the linguistic structure of SLs only began in the 1960s with the seminal work of Stokoe ^[57], whose research on American Sign Language paved the way for social recognition of SLs as real languages. More recent acknowledgment of this is included in the works of linguists such as Pinker ^[39] and Chomsky ^[37]. Increased recognition of SLs as fully formed, independent languages following political acknowledgment, such as the Resolution of the European Parliament in 1986 has led to some level of research being carried out on SLs in most countries. Usually, it is the national center for Deaf Studies or other Deaf associations that investigate the sociological, educational, cultural, and linguistic aspects of SLs.

Like the Europeans, in Africa, there has been some research work. For instance, in Ethiopia recently there is some research focused on the assessment of sexual and reproductive health products and services used by persons with disabilities (including deaf society) and the current status of HIV/AIDS and deafness in Ethiopia ^[17].

Despite common misconceptions, sign languages are not universal.^[9] If they were, there would be no barrier between Deaf communities. The *Ethnologue of world languages* ^[23] catalogs 121 sign languages for the Deaf worldwide. The majority of these languages are distinct languages in their own right that have evolved either naturally within Deaf communities themselves or have originally been borrowed from other SLs.

Although there is no standardized universal SL, there is an International SL often termed Gestuno ^[24] does exist. Rather than being a fully-formed language, it is a vocabulary of signs, more iconic in nature than SLs in general. It is primarily used to facilitate communication in international contexts when there is no common SL. It is not standardized nor does it have its

own grammar. Given this flexibility and lack of native users, International SL can only go so far as to bridge the communication gap between different SL communities. Rather than standardizing an international form of the language which would require tens of thousands of people to learn a new language, never mind the language development needed, this is another area where SL MT could significantly facilitate and improve international communication on the SL level

2.4.2. Ethiopian Sign Language

Ethiopian Sign Language (ESL) is one of the under-researched languages of Ethiopia although it has over a million users in the Deaf community. Not much is known about the language, its use, and its current status. However, there is a growing question of equality, participation, and use of rights which have been emerging among the users of the Deaf community. Until quite recently 22 many people in Ethiopia presume ESL resembles the country’s dominant spoken language, Amharic.

It is believed that Ethiopian Sign Language (ESL) has its origin in American Sign Language (ASL) with some influence from the Nordic countries. According to a report on a pilot survey conducted by SIL Ethiopia (2005), a comparison was done between 249 signs that are published in American and Ethiopian books. Out of this number, 25% of the signs from the ASL that was brought over have been modified to suit Ethiopian culture. This shows that the two languages are more closely related languages than other sign languages. Besides, signers of the two countries are seen to communicate at a lesser communication breakdown.

The first missionaries that opened schools in Addis Ababa were from the US, and as most foreigners that open new schools do, they brought with them the language which was in use in their own country. There was another school in the then-northern province of Eritrea in Karen, which was opened by Missionaries from the Nordic countries. The influence of the graduates of these schools was clearly seen in the development of the Ethiopian Sign Language.

The first work done in ESL was preparing the corresponding sign for the Geez letter by an individual deaf person called Mr. Minase Abera in 1972 ^[60]. This work paved the way to prepare the first national sign language dictionary in 1980 ^[60]. The book was called “የአማርኛ የምልክት ቋንቋ መስማት ለተሳናቸውሀ 1ኛ መጽሐፍ” – Amharic Sign language for the Deaf ha 1st book. This book has 15 chapters, 1009 signs with pictures, and 270 signs without pictures.

Figure 2 - Mr. Minase Abera showing his creation

In 2008 the second dictionary in Ethiopian sign language history and the first book in Ethiopian National Association for the Deaf has published by ENAD with 85 thousand euros in support from Finland's Minister of Foreign Affairs. This dictionary contains 25 chapters, 1322 signs, and 464 pages. Unlike the first Ethiopian sign language dictionary this dictionary is titled “የኢትዮጵያ ምልክት ቋንቋ መዝገቢቃላት” – Ethiopian Sign Language Dictionary.

Figure 3 - Ethiopian Sign Language Dictionary

Ethiopian deaf education is constrained by many factors. Among others is the lack of the development of sign language. The lack of proficient (or nearly the total absence) sign language teachers is another constraint. There are only a few deaf people employed at deaf schools in Addis Ababa without any training in the teaching profession. Only hearing people were trained as teachers of the Deaf. These hearing teachers lack proficiency in Sign Language and tend to promote Oralism or their spoken languages ^[18]. Due to these facts, the Ethiopian Deaf students are denied strong role models in their education. The deaf students were, therefore, subject to the wishes of their hearing teachers and professionals.

The other one is the problem of getting qualified sign language interpreters who are familiar with the ethics and conduct of behavior in Sign language interpreting.

Although there are many aged modern and traditional schools for spoken languages in Ethiopia, before the 1980s there was no means for deaf individuals to go to school and, at least, to develop their communication skills. But in the 1980s Mekanisa Deaf School, the first deaf/signers school in Ethiopia was opened and ESL with the current structure started then. Later in 1992, the first book for the signers was published by Ethiopian Evangelical Church Mekane Yesus – School for the Deaf School (MYSD) - Hosanna, which is intended to help Deaf individuals and their families on how to “speak” using their hands and body gesture and “listen” using eyes.

In addition to deaf schools, by the 2008/2009 Academic year, the Department of Linguistics, Addis Ababa University has launched Ethiopia’s first BA in Ethiopian Sign Language and Deaf Culture program. In the 2008 Academic year, 26 students are permitted to enroll. Out of this number, 20 of them are Deaf students, and the rest 6 hearing. There were three qualified instructors who were teaching the major courses. Besides, each class is supported by Sign language interpreters. There were three committed Sign language interpreters who are serving the students through tutoring.

2.4.3. SL Transcription

So far, we have addressed SLs from a person-to-person communication point of view. This could be compared to a discussion of speech for spoken languages. But we are primarily concerned about SLs for MT; for this, a text or symbolic representation is required. One of the striking differences between sign and spoken languages is the distinct lack of a formally adopted, or even recognized, writing system for SLs. There are many possible reasons for this, one being that as SLs are minority languages, they are poorly resourced as much investment in languages serves to increase the prominence and power of dominant languages and ignore the less significant, minority ones. On a more linguistic level, simultaneous articulation of the phonemic structure of SLs, as described previously in this section, does not lend itself to a linear writing system.

The lack of a formalized or widely used writing system for SLs means that SLs remain as visual-spatial languages that cannot be 'read' as spoken languages can. There have been many attempts at creating writing systems for SLs, but most are not usable by the general public as they consist of numeric codes or symbols to encapsulate the phonetics or phonology of signs and are not easily learned, written nor is there a standardized accepted form. The models discussed in the following sections outline the most commonly used systems and among those the HamNoSys (Hamburg Notation System)

2.5. Business Logic of the current system

As far as we know there are two sectors involved in Sign language learning support schools which are the government and private sectors.

Both sectors follow the same learning methods. That is the traditional way of learning methodology students are obligated to attend all the classes, exams ... etc in person, and the same as for the academic stuff.

The government sector or government schools give some advantages to students who are unable to pay or students who need special needs financially, psychologically ... etc.

Whereas Private Schools don't have that many advantages compared to the government sector. But some private schools support their students financially and psychologically.

Both sectors use the same business scenarios. The student has to be registered which could be with payment or with an entrance exam. Then the student should pay every month to attend any class.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1. Overview

This chapter mainly focuses on requirement specification and analysis for the proposed system (i.e. Ethiopian Sign Language Learning Platform). The chapter begins by stating the functional and non-functional requirements of the proposed method. Next to that different scenarios are written to justify how the problems in the existing system shall be addressed in the proposed approach. we write solutions and draw models for the proposed method using an object-oriented modeling technique. And the final section of this chapter includes a use-case diagram, activity and sequence diagram, class diagram, persistence, and other modeling diagram supported by UML.

3.2. Functional requirement

- ❖ sign language translation to text (detection)
- ❖ Lesson
- ❖ Classroom
- ❖ Exercise
- ❖ Notification system
- ❖ Certification

3.3. Non-functional Requirement

Accessibility

The main idea of Our system is to make the sign language learning platform to be accessible at any time (24 / 7) and from anywhere without any limitations. It is a web-based and if possible, a mobile app, therefore internet connection and platform are required to be accessible.

Availability

Our learning platform system will be available using a web browser and if possible, a mobile app. To increase the availability of our learning platform reliability of the network and some PC specification must be fulfilled based on our requirements

Compatibility

Our platform will use a version control system to make compatibility issues reduce. For our initial release our minimum spec will be as follows:

- GPU - minimum of intel graphics
- CPU - 1.20 GHz
- RAM - 4GB
- Storage - any hard disk type and a minimum of 1.5GB of free space

Since this system is web-based it is compatible with any operating system and all versions of the android smartphone environment if a web browser is installed in the computer, an internet connection is available and the application is installed on the device.

Maintainability

The system will be maintainable. Changes made to our system must not affect the current system state. The system will be easy to maintain at any time of failure. Since the log file is registered along with the error stack, it will be clear to find the bug location and type of bug that happened.

Manageability

Our learning platform is built to have a customizable learning methodology with customizable class students. And it is easily customizable and manageable and the administrators can monitor the system, through critical health status exposed through its monitoring capabilities.

Scalability

This platform can be scaled by adding chat features and video conferences for hearing-impaired communities to easily communicate in job interviews, workplaces... etc.

Performance

The system should respond within a 10sec of time. It depends on the performance of the hardware environment and internet connection speed. As a learning platform, it should perform better to maximize its productivity.

This system requires some serious PC requirements like having GPU (minimum of intel-graphics). When loading for the first time our platform responds with the following response time in a minimum of 100Kb/s downlink and 30Kb/s uplink speed:

- ❖ Loading time: less than 20sec
- ❖ Loading the whole content: less than 40sec
- ❖ Detection compilation (initially to start): 01- 01:20 min

Reliability

Reliability is more important for our platform since our main actors or users are students and teachers it should be reliable depending on the platform version specifications.

Security

Our platform assures all data inside the system or its part will be protected against malware attacks or unauthorized access by using the latest security methodology and tracking each login and activity and notifying the user and administrators.

Usability

The platform is highly useful since it doesn't have any age restrictions. Our is to make this as much as usable for anyone by focusing on user interface and user experience (UI/UX) to be user-friendly.

Error Handling

Every error is tracked and saved in our server and generates an error log file. By recording each error our system will respond to the administrator which could be through email or on our platform. This way errors could be handled based on the severity.

3.4. System Scenario

3.4.1. Scenario 1

Name of use case: Login

Participating instance actor: Anyone (students, admin, teachers, assistant ...etc)

Entry condition:

- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection
- They have to navigate to EthioSignLang.com or launch the app
- The user must be authenticated. A user must have a valid username/password and must login with their username and password which is recognized by the system.

The flow of events:

1. The system displays the sign-in (login) page
2. Fill correct credentials and click login.
3. The user is now authenticated and logged in to the system

Alternate conditions:

- If he/she uses incorrect credentials to login into the system then the system will generate an error message, then he/she is prompted to enter valid information again for a limited attempt.
- When attempting to login into the system with incorrect credentials the system records all login activities and notifies the user.

Exit condition: the system validates the entered credentials and collects login activities.

Special requirement: Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.

3.4.2. Scenario 2

Name of use case: Sign Language Translation

Participating instance actor: Any user (requires users to be authenticated)

Entry condition:

- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection
- They have to navigate to etsl.netlify.app or launch the app

Flow of events:

1. The system displays the translation page
2. The user types any keyword
3. Then the system generates and displays the corresponding GIF of the user's input
4. The user can practice the typed text with the help of ML (sign language detection)

Alternate conditions:

- Display hardware error if the device doesn't meet the minimum requirements
- If the user runs into an error the system will display the type of error and how to solve it.

Exit condition: The system collects all translation activities for system improvements.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-graphics needed

3.4.3. Scenario 3

Name of use case: Sign Language Learning

Participating instance actor: Students

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection
- They have to navigate to EthioSignLang.com or launch the app

Flow of events:

1. The system displays all the chapters
2. The user selects chapter and proceeds
3. Learn based on the lesson plan
4. After finishing the chapters or sub-chapters the student takes an exam or quick exercise
5. Each exercise will be evaluated and reported back to the student
6. **Evaluation:** According to the result the system evaluates if the student should pass or fail.

Exit condition: The student can log-out at any time since the platform is cloud-based everything will be saved.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-graphics is needed.

3.4.4. Scenario 4

Name of use case: Create Classroom

Participating instance actor: Admin, other Roles (Teachers, Students)

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection

Flow of events:

1. Navigate to the Classroom Dashboard
2. Then navigate to create classroom page
3. Fill out the required form
4. Then add email address of students
5. Confirm and submit

6. Then the classroom owner creates custom lessons

7. Submit and exit.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifications the user that the classroom is created successfully.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-UHD graphics needed

3.4.5. Scenario 5

Name of use case: Join Classroom

Participating instance actor: Admin, other Roles (Students)

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection

Flow of events:

1. If there is invitation sent the user will be notified
2. Navigate to notification.
3. The user has two options accept and decline
4. If the user declines the invitation will be deleted and removed from user's notification.
5. If the user accepts, he/she will join the classroom
6. Then the user will start taking the custom lesson that the classroom owner created before and exit.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifications the user that the current lesson is saved successfully.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-UHD graphics needed

3.4.6. Scenario 6

Name of use case: Prepare Exams

Participating instance actor: Admin, other Roles (Teachers)

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The user must be an admin or a teachers
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection
- They have to navigate to EthioSignLang.com or launch the app

Flow of events:

1. Navigate to the exam question page
2. Add new exam questions
3. Fill out the required form
4. Add questions
5. Assign pass and fail parameters
6. Submit and exit.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifies the user that the Exam is created successfully.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-UHD graphics needed

3.4.7. Scenario 7

Name of use case: Prepare Chapters (Lesson plan)

Participating instance actor: Admin, other Roles (Teachers)

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The user must be an admin or a teachers
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection

Flow of events:

1. Navigate to the chapters page
2. Add new chapters
3. Fill out the required form
4. Add chapter content
5. Assign pass and fail parameters
6. Submit and exit.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifies the user that the chapter is created successfully.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-graphics needed

3.4.8. Scenario 8

Name of use case: Personal Account Management

Participating instance actor: Any authenticated user

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection

Flow of events:

1. Navigate to a profile page
2. Enter the current password
3. Perform add, edit or delete operations
4. Submit
5. Logout automatically
6. Redirect to the login page

Alternate conditions: if the password entered is wrong the user cant navigate to the profile page contents.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifies the user that the account has been modified and it is going to log out after 5sec.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-graphics needed

3.4.9. Scenario 9

Name of use case: User Management

Participating instance actor: Admin

Entry condition:

- The user must be logged in to the system
- The user must be an admin
- The device must be compatible with the system requirements
- Must have a stable internet connection

Flow of events:

1. Navigate to the Users page

2. Enter the current password
3. Add new users manually, edit, deactivate or delete any user

Alternate conditions: if the password entered is wrong the user can't navigate to the profile page contents.

Exit condition: The system tells/alerts/notifications the user that the account has been modified and it is going to logout after 5sec.

Special requirement:

- Any web browsers have to be installed/application installed.
- A minimum of Intel-graphics needed

3.5. Use case Model

Use-case model is a scenario-based technique in UML that identifies the actors in an interaction and describes the interaction itself. A set of use cases should describe all possible interactions with the system.

1. Actor identification

Name: Student

Description: The main emphasis of the system is the students and their interaction with the platform is the most crucial.

Rule: Take the Course, take the exam, and get certified

Name: Teacher

Description: A teacher is needed in case of creating a custom classroom and the teacher must be verified based on the status on the platform.

Rule: Create custom Course, assist exam, create classroom and invite students

Name: Admin

Description: Admin have total control of the platform which involves deactivating user, deactivating lessons, deactivating exams, creating, updating, and deleting.

Rule: Total control of the system.

3.5.1. Use case diagram

Figure 4 - Use Case Diagram

3.5.2. Use case description

Use case name	Login/logout
Use case ID	01
Use case description	Authentication of the given username and password
Actor	Administration staff, Student, Guard
Pre-Condition	Users must have a valid username and password
Post-Condition	Redirection towards the main page
Main Flow	Open the website Fill in the required information: Username and Password Click in the login button System Redirect
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password

Table 5 - Use Case Description: Login/logout

Use case name	Text to sign language translation
Use case ID	02
Use case description	Detects sign language in real time from typed Amharic text
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	Log-in and open Ethiopian sign translation
Post-Condition	Provide sign for searched text
Main Flow	Open the website Fill in the required information: Username and Password Click in the login button Type Amharic text and search for sign translation
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Unknown Amharic word Wrongly typed Amharic word Internet connection problem

Table 6 - Use Case Description: Text to sign language translation

Use case name	Lesson plan
Use case ID	03
Use case description	To create lesson plans are premium service to customer
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	See the level of the course and make time management and schedule
Post-Condition	Fixed and stable learning environment
Main Flow	<p>To learn a lesson plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open the website • Fill in the required information: Username and Password Click in the login button • System Redirect <p>To create custom lesson plan</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open the website • Fill in the required information: Username and Password Click in the login button • System Redirects teacher to create lesson dashboard
Exception Flow	<p>Incorrect username or password</p> <p>Internet connection problem</p> <p>Teacher availabilities</p> <p>Invalid input</p>

Table 7 - Use Case Description: Lesson plan

Use case name	Exercise
Use case ID	04
Use case description	For the learners to understand and learn the sign language more they have to have exercise or practice
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	Learn the chapter or lesson
Post-Condition	Be better at signing
Main Flow	<p>Open the website</p> <p>Click in the login button</p> <p>Open the learning page and select the chapter the customer is currently on</p> <p>After finishing the particular lesson practice</p>

Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Internet connection problem
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Table 8 - Use Case Description: Exercise

Use case name	Classroom
Use case ID	05
Use case description	If the customer needs more tutorial aside from what we can provide and is willing to pay for the service the teachers will create their own virtual classroom and invite student.
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	Paying Service fee Search for available teachers
Post-Condition	Private classroom is formed and additional tutorials is given
Main Flow	<p>Student:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open the website • Click in the login button • Open the classroom feature • Search for available teachers • Pay for the service • Get private classroom <p>Teacher:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open website • Click on the login • Create new classroom • Create new courses and guide students
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Banking problem Internet connection problem Teacher availabilities

Table 9 - Use Case Description: Classroom

Use case name	Update dataset
Use case ID	06
Use case description	Add new dataset for the existing dictionary of words
Actor	Admin
Pre-Condition	Know the sign of the new word Train the software the signed language and its translation to text Then add trained dataset to the existing system
Post-Condition	Wider dataset
Main Flow	Search for new words Search for the sign translation of the new word Train the system of the new word Add trained word and sign translation to the existing dataset
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Finding correct sign language for given text Internet connection problem

Table 10 - Use Case Description: Update dataset

Use case name	Notification
Use case ID	07
Use case description	Send notification to student to keep up with their studies or if new feature is added to the system
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	Any change on the system
Post-Condition	Notification message is sent
Main Flow	<p>Student:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check student calendar date log • Check for system updates • Send notification message <p>Teacher:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Check if new student added to his classroom • Check for system updates • Send notification message <p>Admin:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open the website

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fill in the required information: Username and Password Click in the login button • System Redirect
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Internet connection problem Message may not be sent

Table 11 - Use Case Description: Notify user

Use case name	Certification
Use case ID	08
Use case description	Get an authorized certificate after successful completing the courses
Actor	Any Actor (Student, Teacher or Admin)
Pre-Condition	Finish all the courses and pass the quizzes
Post-Condition	Get certificate
Main Flow	Open the website Click in the login button Take courses and quizzes Complete all courses and quizzes Get certified
Exception Flow	Incorrect username or password Getting organizations to authorized the certificate Incorrect input of names of customer Internet connection problem

Table 12 - Use Case Description: Certification

3.6. Object Model

3.6.1. Class Diagram

Class diagram

Figure 5 - Class diagram: The system

Figure 6 - Class diagram: Detection

3.7. Data Dictionary

Class	Attributes	Operations	Descriptions
User	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Name • Id • Email • Password • Phone Number • Role • isAdmin • Account Status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign up() • Sign in() • getUsers() • getUserProfile() • getToken() • addUser() • updateUserProfile() • setAccountStatus() • deleteUser() • verifyLogin() • Sign out() 	<p>Allow Users to sign up, to access sign in, to edit their profile, to activate or deactivate their account and get a valid token to access the system.</p>
My Lesson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lesson Id • User Id • Status • Progress • Certified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getMyLessons() • continueLesson() • takeLesson() • requestRetakeLesson() • getStatus() • getCertified() 	<p>Allows the user to keep track of lessons he or she is taking, get certified after finishing the lesson and get lesson status if the lesson is deactivated or not.</p>
Lesson	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Id • Title • Description • Course • Min Score • Status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getActiveLessons() • getAllLessons() • getLessonsById() • takeLesson() • addLesson() • deleteLesson() • updateLesson() 	<p>Allows the user to get all active lesson and take a lesson from the active one.</p> <p>Allows the admin to create, update, delete, deactivate any lesson, activate any lesson, and get all lessons even if</p>

			it is inactive lesson
My Exercise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise Id • User Id • Status • Progress • Total Score 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getMyExams() • takeExam() • requestRetakeExam() • getScore() • getStatus() • getCertified() 	Allows the user to track his or her exam status, complains, get a score, get a certification....
Exercise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Id • Title • Description • Exam • Min Score Required • Max Score • Status 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getActiveExercise() • getAllExercise() • getExerciseById() • takeExam() • addExercise() • deleteExercise() • updateExercise() 	<p>Allows the user to get active exams and take active exams.</p> <p>Allows the admin to edit, delete, get both active or inactive exams and get specific exercise</p>
Classroom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Class Room Id • Class Room Name • Class Room Description • Collection of User Id • Collection of Teachers id • Status • Lesson Id • Exercise Id 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getStudents() • getTeachers() • getLessonById() • getExercise ById() • getClassRoomStatus() • deactivateClassroom() • closeClassroom() 	<p>Allows users to create a classroom if students need personal assistant, to see the overall status of classroom ...</p> <p>Allows the teacher to delete the classroom or deactivate, to invite students to the classroom, to remove students from the classroom.....</p> <p>Allows the admin to delete the classroom, to deactivate the classroom.....</p>

Account Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User Id • Collection of Exercises Id • Collection of Class Room Id • Collection of Lesson Id • IsAccountActive 		Collects user's overall info like lessons, classrooms they joined, collection of exams taken, the status of the account (is it active or not)
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Table 13 - Data Dictionary

3.8. Dynamic Model

3.8.1. Sequence Diagram

Figure 7 - Sequence diagram: Admin - Add, edit or Delete Lessons

Figure 8 - Sequence diagram: Admin - Add, edit or Delete Classroom

Figure 9 - Sequence diagram: Admin - Add, edit or Delete Exercise

Figure 10 - Sequence diagram: User sign-in

Figure 11 - Sequence diagram: User - Signup

Figure 12 - Sequence diagram: User - Exercise Dashboard

Figure 13 - Sequence diagram: User - Account Dashboard

Figure 14 - Sequence diagram: User - Translation Dashboard

Figure 15 - Sequence diagram: User - Lesson Dashboard

Figure 16 - Sequence diagram: User - Learn Lesson Dashboard

Figure 17 - Sequence diagram: User - Classroom Dashboard

Figure 18 - Sequence diagram: User – Detection

3.8.2. Activity Diagram

An activity diagram describes a system in terms of activities. Activities are states that represent the execution of a set of operations. The completion of these operations triggers a transition to another activity. Activity diagrams are similar to flowchart diagrams in that they can be used to represent control flow (i.e., the order in which operations occur) and data flow (i.e., the objects that are exchanged among operations).

Figure 20 - Activity diagram: Choose Classroom

act Learn a chapter

Figure 21 - Activity diagram: Learning a chapter

Figure 22 - Activity diagram: Take a quiz or exam

Figure 23 - Activity diagram: Detect Image

3.8.3. State chart Diagram

State diagram determines how a class processes events based on their current state. An event is any internal or external trigger that causes the system to change its state. Transition is a state change. It starts from the source to its destination.

Figure 24 - State chart diagram: Login

Figure 25 - State chart diagram: Learning feature

Figure 26 - State chart diagram: Translate

Figure 27 - State chart diagram: Chapter Completion

Figure 28 - State chart diagram: Chapter failed

Figure 29 - State chart diagram: Accept invitation

Figure 30 - State chart diagram: Send invitation

4. SYSTEM DESIGN

4.1. Overview of the System

In this chapter, we are going to see the system design for the Ethiopian sign language learning platform and recognition. This section includes the design goal, the proposed system design, and the object design.

4.2. Purpose of the System Design

The purpose of designing is to show the direction of how the system is built and supplement the system architecture by providing information and data useful and necessary for the implementation of the system. The objective of the design is to model the system with high quality. It details the process of developing, expressing, documenting, and communicating the realization of the architecture of the system through a complete set of design characteristics described in a form suitable for implementation.

4.3. Design Goals

The design goals specify the qualities of the system that should be achieved and addressed during the design of the system. Developers should consider the following design goals.

4.3.1. Performance

In order for our system to give users a good service it should meet the criteria when loading for the first time. our platform responds with the following response time in a minimum of 100Kb/s downlink and 30Kb/s uplink speed:

- Loading time: less than 20sec
- Loading the whole content: less than 40sec

Detection compilation (initially to start): 01- 01:20 min

4.3.2. Dependability

Our system should achieve the following dependability characteristics in order to be available and to resist crashes.

- Robustness – when the system writes wrong inputs the system responds with clear and brief error messages which help the user understand their mistake and enter the correct input.
- Availability -- The system will be available 24/7 as long as there is an internet connection.
- Reliability – the information provided by the system that is presented on the user interface and the database is reliable as it was gathered and researched properly.
- Security -All communication between the server and client apps are encrypted.

4.3.3. Maintenance

The system may encounter failure and need modification to be maintained. And to do that the system should meet the following maintenance criteria.

- Extensibility – we can add new functionality for the system if we want
- Readability – The system will be developed on frameworks that have detailed documentation for every procedure. Hence, we will be referring the documentation to establish a coding standard. Any developer can pick up our work to manage or expand the system.
- Traceability of requirements – We are going to use the functional requirements strictly as a system guideline.

4.3.4. End user

The system will be able to provide the following end user criteria to achieve the best usability by the user.

- Utility - It supports the end users experience of transportation by reducing time and money consumed over a course of time.
- Usability –the system will be able to help user experience a user interface that is engaging and easy to learn.

4.4. Proposed System Architecture

Figure 31 - System Architecture

4.5. Subsystem Decomposition

Figure 32 - Development View: Subsystem Decomposition

4.6. Subsystem Description

Subsystem	Purpose	Class
Learning Platform	Provide users a learning platform with some custom learning options	Classroom Exercise Lessons
Security	To keep the systems integrity and access control strict	Privilege
IOT	To make it user interactive and interesting using camera for sign detection.	Webcam Detection

Table 14 - Subsystem Description

4.7. Persistent Data Management

The purpose of this section is to show the mapping of the objects/classes of the system, identified during the analysis stage, into the corresponding relational database.

Figure 33 - Persistent Data Management diagram: User-Activities

Figure 35 - Persistent Data Management diagram: User

Figure 36 - Persistent Data Management diagram: User-Exam

Figure 37 - Persistent Data Management diagram: Exam

Figure 38 - Persistent Data Management diagram: Classroom

Figure 33 - Persistent Data Management diagram: User-classroom

Figure 33 - Persistent Data Management diagram: Lesson

4.8. Components Diagram

A component diagram describes the organization and wiring of the physical components in a system. Component diagrams are often drawn to help model implementation details and double check that every aspect of the system's required function is covered by planned development. It shows the system in terms of modules. The following diagram shows component diagram of Ethiopian Sign Language Learning Platform, and it shows dependency, interface and relationship between each component:

Figure 39 - Component Diagram

4.9. Database Design

Figure 40 - Database Diagram

Where:
++ indicates foreign key
+ primary key

1.10. Access Control

	Student	Teacher	Admin	Customer (All Actor)
User			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • deleteUser() • addUser() • getUsers() • setAccountStatus() 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sign up() • Sign in() • getUserProfile() • getToken() • updateUserProfile() • setAccountStatus() • Sign out()
My Lesson				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getMyLessons() • continueLesson() • takeLesson() • requestRetakeLesson() • getStatus() • getCertified()
Lesson			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getAllLessons() • addLesson() • deleteLesson() • updateLesson() 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getActiveLessons() • getLessonsById() • takeLesson()
My Exercise			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getMyExams() • takeExam() • requestRetakeExam() • getScore() • getStatus() • getCertified()
Exercise			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getAllExercise() • addExercise() • deleteExercise() • updateExercise() 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getActiveExercise() • getExerciseById() • takeExam()
Classroom		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inviteStudents() • removeStudents() 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • inviteStudents() • removeStudents() 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • getStudents() • getTeachers() • getLessonById() • getExerciseById() • getClassRoomStatus() • deactivateClassroom() • closeClassroom()

Table 15 - Access Control

5. MACHINE LEARNING METHODOLOGY

Researches proposed a sensor-based multilabel classification to categorize isolated signs by processing signals from sEMG and IMUs placed on both the forearms of signers in an integrated manner with some classification and categorization errors. Similarly, other researches proposed a real-time customize glove-based method with five-flex and one accelerometer sensor to recognize sign language gestures and display corresponding text and audible sounds. Generally, **motion gloves sign language prediction** has high limitations in terms of hand tracking and is uncomfortable for users compared to vision-based methods. Like leap motion controllers, they are expensive, time-consuming, and may produce inaccurate calibrations due to wear and tear from the frequent usage of gloves.

5.1. Method of applications

Various research projects have been conducted in recent years regarding sign language recognition. In general, the methods for recognizing sign language can be divided into two general classes: sensor- and vision-based approaches.

1. **The sensor-based approach:** utilizes various sensors that mostly attach to the hands to capture hand gestures. In fact, flex sensors and Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) are to the two most common sensors for tracking hand gestures. These sensors are used to detect the flexion of fingers and orientation of the hand. proposed a low-cost data glove with five flex sensors attached to the fingers.
 - Using an expensive leap motion controller [LMC], researchers have proposed a training method for ASL with a long short-term memory (LSTM) recurrent neural network for handling a sequence of input and yields an average accuracy rate of 91.08%. This proposed model has several limitations due to the leap motion controller because the number of users affects the model accuracy. Furthermore, this method is limited to recognizing only one hand gesture
2. **The vision-based approach:** is an alternative for sign language recognition. This approach utilizes a video camera or visual sensor to capture the movements and analyzes the gestures with certain motion algorithms.

Researches implemented a fingerspelling sign language translator using a CNN to detect ASL and translate its corresponding text and speech in real-time. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 95% with certain limitations; for example, when running the project, the threshold must be monitored to avoid distorted grayscale in the frames if it does not lead to resetting the histogram or looking for appropriate lighting conditions. Additionally, several extensive literatures on train CNNs for continuous SLR with weakly labeled data has been reported. Here, the CNN inside an iterative expectation-maximization algorithm was trained with over 1 million poorly labeled hand gesture images representing

the sign language. However, moderate prediction accuracy was achieved despite using only the prerecorded pictures and videos as the input, which are unsuitable for real-time hand gesture recognition. For continuous SLR with deep learning, a heuristic approach for epenthesis detection to support continuous natural communication between the machine and user was proposed. Although they have reduced classification confusion, they showed good results only when tested individually with more resources needed for implementing an integrated continuous SLR system. Likewise, several studies exist where both static and dynamic gesture recognition were performed using machine learning and deep learning methods.

5.2. Major components used

MediaPipe Hands

MediaPipe is an open-source framework with a hybrid platform that creates pipelines for processing perceptual data, such as images, videos, and audio. It is an extensive approach employed with ML for hand tracking and gesture recognition in real-time. It provides more hand and finger tracking solutions by accurately detecting the sign gestures. Specifically, we employed a MediaPipe Hands pipeline to obtain the landmarks from the hand.

Figure 41 - MediaPipe Hands

TensorFlow

TensorFlow is an end-to-end open-source platform for machine learning. It has a comprehensive, flexible ecosystem of tools, libraries, and community resources that lets researchers push the state-of-the-art in ML and developers easily build and deploy ML-powered applications.

TensorFlow was originally developed by researchers and engineers working on the Google Brain team within Google's Machine Intelligence Research organization to conduct machine learning and deep neural networks research. The system is general enough to be applicable in a wide variety of other domains, as well. TensorFlow provides stable Python and C++ APIs, as well as non-guaranteed backward compatible API for other languages.

Figure 42 - TensorFlow

Google Colab

Google Colab is a cloud-based service that provides a free Jupyter notebook environment for data science and machine learning education and research. It allows users to write, edit and execute code collaboratively in real-time through their browser. Google Colab provides access to GPU and TPU processing, and supports a range of popular machine learning libraries, including TensorFlow, Keras, PyTorch, and OpenCV.

It also integrates with Google Drive for easy data storage and sharing, and allows for the importing of datasets from publicly accessible websites such as Kaggle. Google Colab is a great tool for anyone looking to experiment with machine learning without the need for expensive hardware or software installations.

The reason why we used it is because Colab provides access to free cloud-based GPUs, which can be used to train machine learning models, including ones for sign language recognition. By using Colab's GPUs, we can experiment with different algorithms and architectures, and train models faster than we would on a standard CPU.

Furthermore, Google Colab provides a convenient platform for sharing code and collaborating with others. This is particularly useful for a sign language recognition project where we may need to work with other team members or share our code with a wider community.

In summary, Google Colab offers free access to GPUs that can greatly accelerate the training process for sign language recognition models and also provides a platform for collaboration and sharing of code.

Figure 43 – Google Colab

Cloud storage

Cloud storage is a cloud computing model that stores data on the Internet through a cloud computing provider who manages and operates data storage as a service. It's delivered on demand with just-in-time capacity and costs, and eliminates buying and managing your own data storage infrastructure.

5.3. Steps in development of Sign Language detection

In this detection process we have two parts they are:

1. training
2. Testing

5.3.1 Training

Hand sign recognition and finger gesture recognition can add and change training data and retrain the model.

Hand sign recognition training

Step 1 .Learning data collection

Press "k" to enter the mode to save key points (displayed as [MODE:Logging Key Point])

Figure 44 – Collecting datasets

If you press "0" to "9", the key points will be added to "model/keypoint_classifier/keypoint.csv" as shown below.

```

1  0,0,0,0,-0.09912536443148888,-0.18950437317784258,-0.09620991253644315,-0.42857142857142855,-0.09329446064139942,-0.577259475218659,-0.12244897959183673,
2  0,0,0,0,-0.08974358974358974,-0.1891025641025641,-0.08333333333333333,-0.4230769230769231,-0.08653846153846154,-0.5769230769230769,-0.10576923076923077,-
3  0,0,0,0,-0.09764309764309764,-0.17845117845117844,-0.09764309764309764,-0.4276094276094276,-0.09427609427609428,-0.5824915824915825,-0.12121212121212122,
4  0,0,0,0,-0.10184529616724739,-0.17073170731707318,-0.10184529616724739,-0.42857142857142855,-0.0975609756097561,-0.5888501742160279,-0.1289198606271777,-
5  0,0,0,0,-0.10408921933085502,-0.2044609654275092,-0.10408921933085502,-0.4275092936802974,-0.10037174721189591,-0.5836431226765799,-0.12639405204460966,
6  0,0,0,0,-0.08831908831908832,-0.18803418803418803,-0.08831908831908832,-0.4301994301994302,-0.08831908831908832,-0.5811965811965812,-0.1225071225071225,-
7  0,0,0,0,-0.05042016806722689,-0.1792717086834734,-0.008403361344537815,-0.4005602240896359,0.008403361344537815,-0.5742296918767507,-0.014005602240896359,
8  0,0,0,0,-0.06701030927835051,-0.16237113402061856,-0.030927835051546393,-0.39690721649484534,-0.028350515463917526,-0.5541237113402062,-0.064432989690721,
9  0,0,0,0,-0.0945273631840796,-0.12437810945273632,-0.09203980099502487,-0.373134328358209,-0.08706467661691543,-0.5422885572139303,-0.12437810945273632,-0.
10 0,0,0,0,-0.09549071618037135,-0.15119363395225463,-0.10875331564986737,-0.40318302387267907,-0.10344827586206896,-0.5676392572944297,-0.13793103448275862,
11 0,0,0,0,-0.08823529411764706,-0.14705882352941177,-0.10160427807486631,-0.3983957219251337,-0.10160427807486631,-0.5588235294117647,-0.14171122994652408,
12 0,0,0,0,-0.09510869565217392,-0.15489130434782608,-0.10869565217391304,-0.4048913043478261,-0.10597826086956522,-0.5652173913043478,-0.1358695652173913,
13 0,0,0,0,-0.09329446064139942,-0.1836734693877551,-0.09620991253644315,-0.4198250728862974,-0.10787172011661808,-0.5830903790087464,-0.13411078717201166,
14 0,0,0,0,-0.12251655629139073,-0.17880794701986755,-0.1423841059602649,-0.3973509933774834,-0.15894039735099338,-0.5562913907284768,-0.19205298013245034,-
15 0,0,0,0,-0.146757679180088736,-0.20819112627986347,-0.17064846416382254,-0.40955631399317405,-0.18430034129692832,-0.5631399317406144,-0.2150170648464164,
16 0,0,0,0,-0.14130434782608695,-0.1956521739130435,-0.14855072463768115,-0.40942028985507245,-0.16304347826086957,-0.572463768115942,-0.18840579710144928,-
17 0,0,0,0,-0.07881773399014778,-0.2315270935960591,-0.07881773399014778,-0.46798029556650245,-0.09113300492610837,-0.6231527093596059,-0.13054187192118227,
18 0,0,0,0,-0.07268170426085163,-0.21804511278195488,-0.06516290726817042,-0.46867167919799496,-0.07518796992481203,-0.6290726817042607,-0.11779448621553884,
19 0,0,0,0,-0.0660377358490566,-0.22327044025157233,-0.050314465408005034,-0.4716981132075472,-0.06289308176100629,-0.6383647798742138,-0.11320754716981132,
20 0,0,0,0,-0.05194805194805195,-0.24415584415584415,-0.03116883116883117,-0.4753246753246753,-0.03896103896103896,-0.6363636363636364,-0.07792207792207792,
21 0,0,0,0,-0.06537530266343826,-0.14527845036319612,-0.053268765133171914,-0.3559322033898305,-0.07990314769975787,-0.5012106537530266,-0.12832929782082325,
22 0,0,0,0,-0.06521739130434782,-0.15217391304347827,-0.05314009661835749,-0.35990338164251207,-0.0748792270531401,-0.5048309178743962,-0.1280193236714976,-
23 0,0,0,0,-0.061124694376528114,-0.15158924205378974,-0.0488997555012225,-0.3740831295843521,-0.08068459657701711,-0.5183374083129584,-0.12469437652811736,
24 0,0,0,0,-0.06958762886597938,-0.13402061855670103,-0.06701030927835051,-0.3556701030927835,-0.09020618556701031,-0.5,-0.14175257731958762,-0.631443298969,
25 0,0,0,0,-0.05596107055961071,-0.1435523114355231,-0.04866180048661801,-0.36982968369829683,-0.0827250608272506,-0.5158150851581509,-0.11678832116788321,-
26 0,0,0,0,-0.06629834254143646,-0.15469613259668508,-0.058011049723756904,-0.38950276243093923,-0.08011049723756906,-0.5386740331491713,-0.1270718232044199,
27 0,0,0,0,-0.06142506142506143,-0.16953316953316952,-0.051597051597051594,-0.3783783783783784,-0.07862407862407862,-0.5184275184275184,-0.11793611793611794,

```

Figure 44 - Datasets

After capturing our images, we then create our model.

Using MediaPipe, pre-process images to create multi-hand landmarks.

MediaPipe is a framework that allows developers to create cross-platform multi-modal (video, audio, any time series data) applied machine learning pipelines.

MediaPipe contains a massive array of human body detection and tracking algorithms that have been trained on Google’s vast and diverse dataset. They track critical spots on different body sections as the skeleton of nodes and edges or landmarks. All coordinate points are normalized in three dimensions.

Models created by Google developers using Tensorflow-lite make information flow more adaptive and customizable using graphs. Pipelines in MediaPipe are made up of nodes on a diagram often specified in a text file.

Figure 45 - Hand Tracking Module

Using LSTM Model for model building

To build the model, we use the LSTM model, which includes all these optimizers and activations. To achieve accuracy, the LSTM model is a good option. LSTM networks are recurrent neural networks that may learn order dependence in sequence prediction challenges.

Figure 46 - LSTM Model

In complicated problem areas, this is required behavior. The gates are three elements of an LSTM cell. The Forget gate is the first section, the Input gate is the second, and the Output gate is the third. An LSTM, like a simple RNN, contains a hidden state, with $H(t-1)$ representing the previous timestamp’s hidden state and H_t representing the current timestamp’s secret state. LSTMs also include a cell state, represented by $C(t-1)$ and $C(t)$, respectively, for past and current timestamps.

Choosing an optimizer and calculating the loss:

In this case, I've used the Adam optimizer. And The nature of the problem determines the loss function. For example, [loss='binary cross entropy] is better for a binary classification task, while [loss='categorical cross entropy] is better for a multi-class classification problem. We'll utilize categorical cross-entropy because we're dealing with a multi-class classification problem.

Total Epochs:

During training, the number of epochs refers to the number of times the complete dataset is run through the neural network. There is no perfect number, and it is dependent on the data.

Using ReLU: We're utilizing the ReLU activation function, the most often used activation function in neural networks, because of its computational simplicity (among other advantages). For negative inputs, this function returns zero; for positive information, it returns the value itself. ReLU is the default activation function for most current neural networks. Sigmoid, Tanh and other activation functions are also used.

Checking the Test Accuracy

After checking the training accuracy, it becomes crucial to check the testing accuracy using the test dataset we have. It is done to prevent the final accuracy of the model and study how accurately our model can detect our gestures. We can save this model further so that it can be loaded anytime we want, and by keeping our model, the model's accuracy will remain failed so that we don't have to deal with varied accuracy each time we run the model.

Stage 2: Hosting the model on Cloud Object(Google Drive) Store for deployment

It's essential to have good database space as the number of images will be very high. To train the model and increase the accuracy, it is necessary to have many photos. Cloud storage is critical to store these images as it helps in the faster fetching and execution of the dataset.

With the loud comes the security provided by cloud storage. It becomes imperative to see the enormous size of the dataset if we use American Sign Language or Indian Sign Language.

The cloud storage will be divided into two parts:

Train data Storage: All the images here will be used for training the model and finding the training accuracy of the model.

Test/Validation data storage: All the images here will be used to generate the test/validation accuracy of the model.

Stage 3 : Model training

Open "keypoint_classification.ipynb" in Google Colab and execute from top to bottom.

To change the number of training data classes, change the value of "NUM_CLASSES = 3" and modify the label of "model/keypoint_classifier/keypoint_classifier_label.csv" as appropriate.

X.Model structure

Figure 47 – Mediapipe neural network

5.3.2 Tesing

Testing is an essential part of machine learning development, as it allows us to assess the performance of our trained model in a realistic scenario.

Step 1: Capture Images from webcam for object detection

Step 2: Real-time detections with custom TensorFlow sign language model.

6. IMPLEMENTATION

6.1. Overview

In this section we strive to define the process of the information system that should be built (i.e., physical system design), whether the system is operational and used, and if or not the system meets the quality standards (i.e., quality assurance).

6.2. Coding Standard

Coding Standards, also known as coding conventions, are a set of agreed-upon rules that developers follow to ensure the reusability, efficiency, and readability of the written code. These rules or conventions often cover the organization, indentation, comments, declarations, statements, white space, naming conventions, programming practices, programming principles, programming rules of thumb, architectural best practices, etc.

As it is stated previously in this documentation, the main 4 programming languages/ frameworks we are using for this project are React JS, Node JS, and Python. We have listed below the coding standards used for each of these languages/ frameworks with their brief description.

1. **React JS:** is designed to ensure that code is written in a consistent, readable, and maintainable way. Generally, coding standards for React JS include guidelines for naming conventions, formatting, and best practices for code structure. For example, React code should be organized into separate files for each component, and files should be named in camelCase. Additionally, React components should be written in ES6 and use prop types to define all props. Furthermore, code should strive to be DRY (Don't Repeat Yourself) and should use linting and automatic formatters to ensure consistency. Finally, while React allows for the use of JavaScript classes, it is generally recommended to use Functional Components over class-based components.
2. **Node JS:** The Node.js coding standard sets out guidelines for formatting and linting code, using environment variables and configuration for sensitive data, naming conventions for variables, constants, functions, and classes, and other best practices for software development. Additionally, it is recommended to use a style guide, such as the Google JavaScript Style Guide, when coding in Node.js, to ensure consistency and readability. It is also recommended to use all constants, functions, variables, and class names in lowercase when declaring them, as well as to avoid single-line ternary operators, as they can be difficult to read.
3. **Python:** Python coding standards and best practices help ensure that code is maintainable, readable, and easy to understand. These standards include: using meaningful variable names, breaking code into meaningful sections, indenting code properly, using comments to explain code, and avoiding global variables. Additionally, it is important to follow the

Python coding style guide (PEP 8), which is a set of rules for formatting Python code to make it more consistent and easier to read. Following coding standards and best practices helps to ensure that code is well-structured and maintainable and can help to make code easier for others to understand.

6.3. Prototype

The Prototype implemented for this project satisfies the minimum requirement of performing CRUD operations for specific features. Because the project has both a hardware and software aspect, this prototype is for the software aspects of the project.

The Prototype consists of the web app connected with the backend or REST API performing CRUD operations. This means the prototype can perform the Create, Read, Update and Delete operations on one specific feature across the web and mobile apps. The prototype is developed with the frameworks listed in the previous section.

6.4. Implementation Detail

6.4.1. Client-side

This is the part of the application where it runs on the user's machine. Since users have different kinds of devices with different kinds of capacity client performance should be optimized as much as possible.

The client-side implementation of this project consists, of a web app with an active camera. Let us explore each one closely.

Web app

In the web app, any type of user can perform everything they need to interact and manage their account as well as have access to a responsive well-oiled system ready to serve them at their pleasure.

Three types of users can access the web app, Admin, Teachers, and Students. As such, their privileges are different as well as their experience. Below are the features the web app offers to its users

- Activity history
- User management
- Learn Lessons
- Classroom
- Exercise
- Manage Lessons
- Manage Classroom

→ Manage Exercise

The client-side (web app) implementation was carried out using the following technologies:

React JS framework: is an open-source JavaScript library for building user interfaces. It is maintained by Facebook and a community of individual developers and companies. React is used for creating interactive user interfaces, such as single-page applications, mobile applications, and web applications. React provides an easy-to-use syntax for creating components, which are then used to compose complex UIs. React has gained popularity due to its flexibility and performance, making it a popular choice for developing web apps.

Tensorflow JS: is an open-source hardware-accelerated JavaScript library for training and deploying machine learning models. It is built on top of TensorFlow, which makes it easy to use and train models in the browser or in Node.js. TensorFlow.js models can be trained using a variety of architectures and algorithms, and it also provides flexible and intuitive APIs to build and deploy models. Additionally, TensorFlow.js provides a WebAssembly (WASM) backend for both the browser and for Node.js, allowing for real-world applications of the library. It is also used for projects such as PoseNet, which runs in the browser and prevents pose data from ever leaving a user's computer

React Redux: is a library for React and Redux applications that provides bindings for React components to access the Redux store. It is designed to help developers keep their code organized, allowing them to separate their business logic from their UI components. React Redux enables developers to use the Redux architecture in their React applications, allowing them to easily manage their application state and create performant and scalable applications

6.4.2. Server Side

This is the part of the application where the client apps and devices request services from the server and the server returns the requested query or function to the aforementioned apps and devices.

The server-side (REST API) implementation was carried out using the following technologies:

MongoDB database is an open-source document database and a leading NoSQL database. It is classified as a NoSQL database program and uses JSON-like documents with schema

Node JS framework: is an open-source, cross-platform JavaScript runtime environment that allows developers to create server-side and network applications. Popular frameworks for Node.js development include Express.js, Nest.js, and Electron.

Express.js framework: is a Node.js web application framework that provides a robust set of features for web and mobile applications. It is designed to be minimal, and flexible, and provide a wide range of features for web and mobile applications. Express.js simplifies the process of writing web applications and APIs and provides features such as routing, middleware, and template engines. It is also compatible with a wide range of languages and databases. Express.js is a great choice for building web applications and APIs, as it is both fast and powerful.

6.5. Deployment

We have two kinds of deployment The Client-Side or Frontend Deployment and Server-Side or REST API deployment

Frontend Deployment

React is a SPA (Single Page Application) framework with static data which could be deployed on any server which supports languages like HTML, CSS, and JS.

To deploy a React application, we can use a number of different methods, such as deploying to a static web host, using a service like Vercel, or deploying to a cloud platform like AWS or Azure. For detailed instructions on how to deploy a React application, you can refer to the official React documentation. Additionally, there are many tutorials and guides available online that provide step-by-step instructions on how to deploy your React app.

We also have Ethiopian Hosting service providers like Hahu Cloud, Yegara Host etc which support the Deployment of React.

REST API Deployment

REST API (also known as RESTful API) is an application programming interface (API or web API) that conforms to the constraints of Representational State Transfer (REST). REST APIs provide a way for two computer systems to communicate with each other securely over the internet. REST APIs are used to retrieve data from a server and make changes to the data stored on the server. The REST API uses HTTP requests such as GET, POST, PUT, and DELETE to access and modify the data stored on the server. In addition, REST APIs employ authentication methods such as Basic Auth, OAuth, and JWT to ensure that only authorized users can access the data

To deploy a Node.js REST API, you will need to install the necessary software, create a remote database, create the Node server, and then deploy the API to your chosen hosting provider. Commonly used hosting providers include Amazon Web Services, Azure App Service, and Google Cloud Platform. Each of these providers offers different tools and services for deploying Node.js applications, and you should review the documentation for each provider to determine which best suits your needs. Once you have chosen a hosting provider, you can use a tool to invoke REST APIs to deploy the Node.js server. The deployment rule should contain variables that can specify input values for the invocation, such as the API URL and any credentials needed to authenticate the request. Finally, you will need to test the API to ensure that it is working correctly

We also have Ethiopian Hosting service providers like Hahu Cloud, Yegara Host etc which support the Deployment of REST API.

Trained Model Deployment

Lastly, we have the deployment of the trained model. The trained model can be deployed with the front end or with the REST API.

Since we have 2 options for hosting the trained model due to the following reasons the models are going to be hosted in the REST-API or server-side deployment.

1. The trained model is a private file that has to be protected or only authenticated users can get this model from the server. This kind of task could be handled on the server side.
2. On the server side it is easy to configure which app should be allowed or disallowed, which helps to filter unauthenticated requests and block them.

Figure 45 - Deployment Diagram

6.6. User Interface Design

User Interface (UI) Design is the process of creating and optimizing user interfaces to enable people to interact with digital products and services. This typically involves structuring, sizing, positioning, and organizing particular elements on a page or within a digital environment to create an intuitive, interactive user experience. UI Design focuses on delivering an engaging experience for users by recognizing the importance of user input and feedback such as colors, typography, and images to cater for individual's needs.

Figure 46 - User Interface Design: Create account

Figure 47 - User Interface Design: Login

Figure 48 - User Interface Design: Home

Figure 49 - User Interface Design: Platform Page

Figure 50 - User Interface Design: Taking lesson

7. USER MANUAL

7.1. Account Registration

Step 1: Access the Registration Page

- Open your preferred web browser and navigate to our website.
- Look for the "Sign Up" or "Register" button/link on the homepage or navigation menu.
- Click on the "Sign Up" or "Register" button/link to proceed to the registration page.

Step 2: Enter User Information

- On the registration page, you will be prompted to enter your desired username and password.
- Username:
 - Choose a username that is 4 or more characters in length.
 - The username must be unique and not already taken by another user.
 - Avoid using any personal information or sensitive data as your username.
- Password:
 - Create a password that is more than 5 characters long.
 - Include a combination of uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and special characters for a stronger password.
 - It is recommended to choose a unique password that is not easily guessable.
 - Remember that the password is case-sensitive.

Step 3: Confirm Password

- After entering your desired password, you will see a field labeled "Confirm Password."
- Re-enter your chosen password exactly as you typed it before to ensure they match.
- The password in this field should be identical to the one you entered previously.

Step 4: Submit Registration

- Once you have entered your username and password, and ensured that the confirm password field matches, review the information you provided.
- Double-check for any typing errors or mistakes.
- If everything looks correct, click on the "Sign Up" button to submit your registration.

Step 5: Account Verification (if applicable)

- Depending on the platform's policies, you may need to verify your account before gaining full access.
- Check your email associated with the registration for any verification instructions or confirmation link.
- Follow the provided instructions to complete the verification process.

Step 6: Successful Registration

- After completing the registration process and any necessary verification steps, you will receive a confirmation message.
- Congratulations! You have successfully registered for an account on our platform.
- You can now log in using your newly created username and password to enjoy the features and services provided.

Remember to keep your login credentials secure and avoid sharing them with anyone. If you encounter any issues during the registration process or have any questions, please refer to the platform's support documentation or contact our customer support team for assistance.

Figure 51 - User Sign Up Process

7.2. Account Sign-In

This user manual will guide you through the process of signing in to your account. Please follow the steps below to successfully access your account.

Step 1: Access the Sign-In Page

- Open your preferred web browser and navigate to our website.
- Look for the "Sign In" button on the homepage or navigation menu.
- Click on the "Sign In" button to proceed to the sign-in page.

Step 2: Enter Login Credentials

- On the sign-in page, you will be prompted to enter your login credentials.
- Enter your registered email address in the designated field.
- Password:
 - Enter the password associated with your account in the password field.
 - The password is case-sensitive, so ensure you enter it correctly.

Step 3: Review Information

- Double-check the email address and password you entered to make sure they are accurate and free of any typing errors.
- If there are any mistakes, use the backspace key to correct them.

Step 4: Submit Sign-In Request

- Once you have entered your email address and password, review the information you provided.
- Ensure that the login credentials are accurate and match the ones associated with your registered account.
- If everything looks correct, click on the "Sign In" button to submit your sign-in request.

Step 5: Successful Sign-In

- If the email address and password you provided match the records in our system, you will be successfully signed in to your account.

- You will be redirected to your account dashboard .

Remember to keep your login credentials confidential and avoid sharing them with anyone. If you have any questions or need further assistance, please refer to the platform's support documentation or contact our customer support team.

7.3. Take Lesson

Step 1 Choose Lesson Platform

Figure 52 - Step-1

Step 2 Choose Lesson from list of lessons

Figure 53 - Step-2

Step 3 Click Start-Lesson button

Figure 54 - Step-3

Step 4 Conformation

Figure 55 - Step-4

Step 5 Success message displayed and will allow you to press and start the lesson

Figure 56 - Step-5

Step 6 Lesson starts

Figure 57 - Step-6

Step 7 Click next or previous button to navigate (auto save)

Figure 58 - Step-7

Step 8 After Finishing the lesson it navigate to Dashboard here is the UI

Figure 59 - Step-8

7.4. Take Exam

Step 1 Choose Exam Platform

Figure 52 - Step-1

Step 2 Choose Exam from list of exams

Figure 53 - Step-2

Step 3 Click Start-Exam button

Figure 54 - Step-3

Step 4 Conformation

Figure 55 - Step-4

Step 5 Success message displayed and will allow you to press and start the lesson

Figure 56 - Step-5

Step 6 Exam starts

Figure 57 - Step-6

Step 7 Click next or previous button to navigate (auto save)

Figure 58 - Step-7

Step 8 After Finishing the lesson it navigate to Dashboard here is the UI

Figure 59 - Step-8

Figure 60 - Step-8

7.5. To check activities

Step 1 : go to My Activities then choose any platform option

Figure 61 - to check activities

7.6. To edit, delete or create

step-by-step description of instructions .

1. Locate and click on the "Management" option in the navigation menu.
2. After clicking on the "Management" option, a drop-down menu or a new page may appear. Look for options related to the content you mentioned, such as "Lessons," "Classrooms," or "Exams."
3. Click on the appropriate option, depending on which content you want to edit. For example, if you want to edit lessons, click on "Lessons."
4. Once you have selected the desired option, you will be redirected to a page where you can manage and edit the corresponding content. This page may contain a list of all the lessons, classrooms, exams, or other items that have been created.
5. Locate the specific item you want to edit. This can be done by scrolling through the list or using search filters, if available.
6. Once you have found the item you want to edit, look for an "Edit" button, pencil icon, or a similar editing option next to it. Click on this button/icon to initiate the editing process.
7. Depending on the platform or application, a new page or a pop-up window will open, allowing you to modify the

details of the selected item. Here, you can make changes to the lesson, classroom, exam, or other relevant content.

8. After making the necessary edits, review them to ensure accuracy and completeness.

9. Once you are satisfied with the changes, look for a "Save," "Update," or "Apply" button on the editing page. Click on this button to save your modifications.

10. The changes you made should now be implemented and reflected in the corresponding item, such as the lesson, classroom, or exam.

Figure 62 - to manage lesson, classroom or exam

7.6. Profile

Step 1 :go to profile page , you will find it in the sidebar or in the nav dropdown option

Step 2 : This page is protected page so you will be asked to enter your password to edit or perform any action

Figure 62 -Locked Profile page

Step 3 : After entering password you will be redirected to the profile page

Figure 62 - Unlocked profile page

Step 4 : then you can navigate to any tab and perform any action

8. System Testing

8.1 Overview

In this section we will identify test procedures, resources and test cases that will be implemented to ensure an error free platform by employing the listed actions.

- By testing out all possible scenarios
- By listing all the recommended test requirements
- By carrying out user testing.

8.2 Scope

This testing documentation will be imposed on the following System and Version

<i>System Name</i>	Ethiopian Sign Language Platform with Detection
<i>System Description</i>	This system is desinged for anyone who wants to learn and be certified in ethiopian sign language.
<i>System Version</i>	1.4.9
<i>Type</i>	Web-App + Detection

The overall testing plan will include testing all the modules individually and the integration of the modules. The unit tasks of this testing documentation is:

- Test the usability of all platforms (Web + Detection)
- Test the functionality of all features employed in all platforms
- Test the systems tolerance for faulty data

8.3 Resource

We will be using Ethiopian sign language Resource as a main source for the testing process. (Add if there are any testing resources we could have used)

8.4 Roles

<i>Roles</i>	<i>Minimum Resource Recommended</i>	<i>Responsibilities</i>
<i>Test Manager</i>	Yeabsira Adem Feven Asnake	Provides management oversight Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Provide technical direction ● Acquire appropriate resources ● Management reporting
<i>Test Designer</i>	Nanati Oumer	Identifies, prioritizes, and implements test cases Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Generate test plan ● Generate Test Suite ● Evaluate effectiveness of test effort
<i>System Tester</i>	Yeabsira Adem	Executes the tests Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Execute tests ● Log results ● Recover from errors ● Document defects
ML Tester	Nanati Oumer Feven Asnake	
<i>Test System Administrator</i>	Yeabsira Adem Feven Asnake	Ensures test environment and assets are managed and maintained. Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administer test management system ● Install / manage worker access to test systems
<i>Database Administration</i>	Yeabsira Adem	Ensures test data (database) environment and assets are managed and maintained. Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Administer test data (database)
<i>Designer</i>	Nanati Oumer Eyob Birhanemeskel	Identifies and defines the operations, attributes, and associations of the test classes Responsibilities:

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Identifies and defines the test class(es) ● Identifies and defines the test packages
<i>Implementer</i>	Yeabsira Adem Feven Asnake Nanati Oumer Eyob Birhanemeskel	Implements and unit tests the test classes and test packages Responsibilities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Creates the test classes and packages implemented in the Test Suite.

8.5 Schedule

The testing schedule for the proposed system will be conducted in the following manner.

<i>Milestone Tasks</i>	<i>Effort</i>	<i>Date of testing</i>
Test planning	3	June 20, 2023
Test Design	2	June 20, 2023
Test Development	4	June 21, 2023
Test Execution	2	June 21, 2023
Test Evaluation	1	June 22, 2023

8.6 Test case Scenarios and Requirements

The listing below identifies those items (use cases, functional requirements, non-functional requirements) that have been identified as targets for testing. This list represents what will be tested.

8.6.1 Data and Database Integrity Testing

- Verify access to User Database.
- Verify correct retrieval of update of database data.

8.6.2. Function Testing

Verify registration and login.

- user registration and login

Verify Test Lesson Registration

- Lesson registration

Verify Test Exam Registration

- Exam registration

-

Verify Test Lesson

- Taking lesson
- Retaking lesson
- Save each state
- Return report

Verify Test Exam

- Taking exam
- Retaking exam (returns 403 error with “admin have not allowed” message)
- Save each state (with corresponding message displayed)
- Return report (status of the exam ...)

Verify Test Management

- Management for exam (CRUD)
- Management for lesson(CRUD)
- Management for user(CRUD)
- Management for My Exam (CRUD)
- Management for My Lesson(CRUD)

8.6.3. User Interface Testing

- Verify ease of navigation through a sample set of screens.
- Verify sample screens conform to GUI standards.

8.6.4. Performance Testing

- Verify response time to Login.
- Verify response time to get lesson , exam and user info.
- Verify response time for Taking Lesson and Taking Exam.
- Verify response time for detecting sign language.

8.6.5. Load Testing

Testing the capacity of the Learning Platform to handle a considerable amount of load is an important aspect of the testing process. As such we have performed a load test of the system. This was achieved by simulating a large number of devices, 10 to be exact, to send requests to our backend server.

The Load test had received areas where the system could be further optimized but overall, the system has passed its load test.

8.6.6. Security and Access Testing

- Verify Login from a local PC.
- Verify Login from smart phones.
- Verify Login security through user name and password mechanisms.

8.7 Estimated Risk

The major risks that may hinder the testing and verification process are as follows:

- Examination Timmer
- Not meeting schedule deadlines.
- Shortage of technical skills to perform required testing.
- Shortage of budget to conduct testing.

8.8 Contingency plan

The contingency plan to combat the aforementioned risks are:

- Conduct testing with minimum and available budget as possible.
- Compile progress and show to stakeholders even if the testing is not fully completed.
- Perform load and stress testing with available resource.

8.9 Test case Scenarios

8.9.1 ML test cases

Once you have trained your sign language recognition model, we tested how well it performs on new data. Here's the process for testing a machine learning model:

- 1. Split our dataset:** Divide the dataset into two parts - one for training and the other for testing. The split can be typically done as 80/20 - use 80% of data for training and the remaining 20% of data for testing.
- 2. Prepare test data:** For the test set, we needed to prepare the data in the same way we prepared our training data, including any normalization or transformation steps. It's important to ensure that the test dataset is representative of real-world data.
- 3. Run predictions on the test set:** Pass the test set through the model and get its predictions. This will give us an idea of how well the model is generalizing to new data.
- 4. Evaluate accuracy:** Compare the predicted results against the actual results in the test set. we used metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and confusion matrix to evaluate the performance of your model.

Figure 76 –Classification Report for accuracy

5. Tweak and retest: If our model is not performing well, tweak our model by experimenting with different architectures, algorithms, or hyper parameters, then retest our model.

6. Test on unseen data: Finally, after fine-tuning our model, we can test it on real-world or unseen data to see how well it performs.

Figure 77 – Testing with unseen data

Chapter 9: Conclusion and Recommendation

9.1. Conclusion

This project, named Ethiopian Sign Language Learning platform with detection, has required the analysis of one of the most important things in hearing impaired community.

The challenges faced during this project are a lack of datasets and enough resources . Despite these challenges, we have designed and developed a sample sign language learning platform that would benefit hearing impaired community.

9.2. Recommendation

Based on this project, we recommend that the Ethiopian National Association of the Deaf (ENAD) , or government and private school to implement a system by which it can benefit the community.

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